

DISSEMINATION OF DIGITALIZATION OF BRANDING, MARKETING, AND SALES OF UMKM COMMUNITY PRODUCTS IN GEMPOL DISTRICT, PASURUAN REGENCY, EAST JAVA

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ABSTRACT

E-Marketing is one of the marketing media trends that is currently in great demand by the public to support various activities carried out. Slowly but surely, society is starting to leave the conventional or traditional marketing model and switch to modern marketing, namely digital marketing. With E-Marketing, communication and transactions can be done at any time and can reach all corners of the world. With the number of social media users, both chat-based and applications, increasing day by day and can open up opportunities for MSMEs and home businesses to expand their market wings using smartphones. The Gempol MSME Community consists of entrepreneurs who have different products. Based on data taken from the Pasuruan Regency website, the Gempol area has a majority of home businesses in the field of food and beverage processing. The problems of MSMEs that are still often encountered in running their businesses are related to HR, capital and marketing problems. The implementation of this community service uses direct training and mentoring methods with a community development approach. After the root of the problem is known, the next step is to formulate material according to the needs of the target subject. The needs desired by the subject are the installation of WhatsApp Business and the creation of a website as a means of branding, marketing, and increasing product sales from the Gempol UMKM community.

Keywords: *Digitalization, Branding, Marketing, Sales, UMKM Community, Products*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information technology currently impacts society in supporting various business activities, both large and small, to be recognized globally (Pradiani, 2018). The real impact that can be seen is that it can increase sales volume and profit in all businesses, both from the MSME sector and households, to companies.

The number of competitors is the main factor that helps entrepreneurs enter a world of very tight competition (Pradiani, 2018). The right marketing and media strategies are used to be able to reach the target market so that the sales volume of these entrepreneurs always increases and make a profit.

The impact of this information technology can develop aspects of entrepreneurial capabilities and the way the industry survives has developed in line with the creative economy paradigm, where innovative, proactive, and risk-taking aspects are not enough in the context of the knowledge economy. Aspects of internal management and risk, the spirit of anti-plagiarism design, and the ability to create unique differentiating power are crucial aspects in the development of the creative industry today. The ability to manage and process ideas that continue to be the main capital for industrial entrepreneurs, in addition to aspects of technological innovation and marketing, are crucial driving forces of the industry (Hermawan et al., 2017).

E-Marketing is one of the marketing media trends that is currently in great demand by the public to support various activities carried out. Slowly but surely, society is starting to leave the conventional marketing model and switch to modern marketing, namely digital marketing. With E-Marketing, communication, and transactions can be done at any time and can reach remote parts of the world. The number of social media users, both chat-based and applications, increasing day by day and can open up opportunities for MSMEs and home businesses to expand their market wings using smartphones.

Digital technology allows a business to develop new-generation products. Several companies are developing and marketing various products digitally. These products are designed for the business and consumer markets (Pradiani, 2018). Digital products have two categories, namely the content category and the technology category. Digital content consists of information in digital format including video, audio, text, and graphics. The content is converted into business and consumer products such as newspapers, magazines, online games, photos, graphics, and videos. Digital technology is the equipment used by businesses and consumers to develop, store, distribute, and use digital content. This technology ranges from digital video and audio equipment to mobile phones, and personal digital assistants.

The research aims to empower and elevate the capabilities of micro, small, and medium enterprises (UMKM) within the Gempol District by integrating digital technologies into their business processes. This study seeks to address the challenges faced by local entrepreneurs in branding, marketing, and sales by providing them with the necessary knowledge and tools to transition from traditional methods to digital platforms. One of the primary objectives of the research is to enhance the understanding of UMKM business owners about the importance of digital branding. Branding in the digital era involves more than just creating a recognizable logo or slogan; it requires establishing a strong online presence that resonates with the target audience. By educating these entrepreneurs on the nuances of digital branding, the research aims to help them create a more impactful and consistent brand identity that can compete effectively in the digital marketplace.

Moreover, the research focuses on the digitalization of marketing strategies for UMKM products. Traditional marketing methods often have limited reach and can be resource-intensive. The study aims to demonstrate how digital marketing, through channels such as social media, search engines, and email campaigns, can provide a cost-effective and far-reaching solution. By adopting digital marketing strategies, UMKM businesses in Gempol District can expand their market reach beyond local boundaries, accessing national and even international markets.

The research also emphasizes the digitalization of sales processes, guiding UMKM businesses on how to utilize e-commerce platforms, mobile payment systems, and other digital tools to streamline their sales operations. This aspect of the research is crucial in helping businesses increase their sales volumes, improve customer satisfaction, and ultimately, boost their profitability. By equipping local entrepreneurs with the skills to sell their products online, the research aims to contribute to the economic development of the Gempol District by enabling these businesses to thrive in a digitally-driven economy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Digital Branding

According to Fadly & Utama (2020), branding encompasses a name, term, sign, symbol, design, or a combination of these elements, all of which are intended to identify the goods or services of a particular seller or group of sellers and differentiate them from those of competitors. In the context of digital marketing, the role of digital branding is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of online marketing strategies. Without proper branding, it becomes challenging for products to stand out in the marketplace and be easily recognized by consumers.

Rangkuti (2002) further categorizes the concept of a brand into four distinct types: 1) Brand name, which refers to the verbal or written part of the brand that identifies and distinguishes the product; 2) Brand mark, which includes the visual elements of the brand such as logos or symbols that are recognized by consumers; 3) Trade mark, which is the legal protection given to the brand elements to safeguard them from unauthorized use; and 4) Copyright, which protects the creative aspects of the brand such as slogans or jingles.

Branding, therefore, is not merely about creating a symbol or name but also involves building recognition and trust for the product in the eyes of the public. By developing a strong digital brand, businesses can significantly enhance the impact of their online marketing efforts. The synergy between digital branding and online marketing can create a powerful and efficient sales system, ensuring that goods and services are not only recognized but also preferred by consumers in a competitive digital marketplace.

2.2 Digital Marketing and Sales

According to Kotler (2011), online marketing is a performance system utilized by companies to sell goods, services, or promote offerings by leveraging the internet as a central component of the system (Fadly & Utama, 2020). This form of marketing is

commonly referred to as e-commerce, where the internet serves as the primary medium for conducting transactions, making the shopping experience more accessible and efficient for consumers. One of the key advantages of online marketing is the simplification and efficiency of the payment process. Consumers can easily make payments through various methods, such as ATMs (Automatic Teller Machines) or online banking services, without the need for physical cash exchanges.

In addition to the ease of payment, online marketing also offers the convenience of product accessibility. Customers can browse, view, and purchase products online without needing to visit a physical store or sales location. This convenience is further enhanced by the integration of delivery services, which ensure that purchased products are delivered directly to the buyer's doorstep. This aspect of online marketing is particularly beneficial in a country like Indonesia, where a significant portion of the population already uses smartphones.

The effectiveness of online marketing has been further amplified by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has led to an increase in remote working or "work from home" practices. With more people spending time at home, the reliance on online shopping and digital transactions has grown, making online marketing an essential tool for businesses to reach their customers. The combination of convenience, efficiency, and widespread smartphone usage has made online marketing a highly effective strategy in the current economic climate.

III. METHODOLOGY

The implementation of this community service project employs direct training and mentoring methods within the framework of a community development approach. This approach focuses on empowering the community by positioning them as both the subject and object of development, ensuring their active participation and engagement in the service activities (Setiyanti, 2022). The methodology begins with a thorough observation of the needs and challenges faced by the Gempol MSME community. This initial step is crucial for accurately identifying the root causes of the problems that hinder the community's growth and digital adoption. Once these issues are clearly understood, the next step involves formulating training material tailored to the specific needs of the community members. In this case, the community expressed a strong interest in learning how to install and use WhatsApp Business and how to create a website, which are critical tools for branding, marketing, and enhancing product sales.

The third step in the methodology is the execution of training sessions and ongoing mentoring for digital marketing. This phase focuses on the practical use of WhatsApp Business and the development of free websites as platforms for the Gempol MSME group. The hands-on training ensures that participants not only learn the necessary skills but also receive continuous support as they apply these skills in real-time. The expected outcomes of this community service activity are the successful installation of the WhatsApp Business application on participants' smartphones and the creation of functional websites for their businesses. These outcomes are designed to equip the Gempol MSME community with the tools and knowledge needed to

effectively market their products, improve their digital presence, and ultimately increase their sales and business sustainability.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

E-Marketing, or electronic marketing, is a contemporary approach to marketing that leverages digital channels and platforms to promote products and services. This trend has gained significant traction in recent years as more businesses and consumers transition from traditional marketing methods to digital ones. The appeal of E-Marketing lies in its ability to facilitate instant communication and transactions, enabling businesses to connect with their target audiences at any time and from anywhere in the world. One of the key advantages of E-Marketing is its broad reach. Unlike conventional marketing, which often relies on physical presence and geographical proximity, digital marketing can penetrate markets that are geographically distant or previously inaccessible. This global reach is particularly beneficial for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) as well as home-based businesses, allowing them to compete on a larger scale without the need for significant physical infrastructure. By utilizing digital tools such as social media, email campaigns, and search engine marketing, these businesses can effectively target specific demographics and tailor their marketing efforts to meet the needs of diverse customer segments.

The rise of social media platforms has further fueled the growth of E-Marketing. Social media, with its billions of users worldwide, offers businesses a unique opportunity to engage with customers in a more personalized and interactive manner. Whether through chat-based applications, such as WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger, or visual-centric platforms like Instagram and TikTok, businesses can create compelling content that resonates with their audience. Moreover, the interactive nature of social media allows for real-time feedback, enabling businesses to quickly adapt their strategies based on customer responses and preferences. Another significant benefit of E-Marketing is its cost-effectiveness. Traditional marketing methods, such as print advertising or television commercials, often require substantial financial investment. In contrast, digital marketing campaigns can be executed at a fraction of the cost, making them accessible to businesses with limited budgets. This democratization of marketing means that even small businesses and startups can leverage E-Marketing to compete with larger, more established companies.

The rapid advancement of information technology has brought profound changes to various sectors, including business, where its impact is particularly evident. This technological evolution plays a crucial role in enabling businesses of all sizes, from micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) to large corporations, to gain global recognition. One of the most tangible effects of this is the increase in sales volume and profitability across different business sectors. In today's competitive landscape, where the number of competitors is ever-growing, the ability to leverage information technology effectively becomes a key determinant of success. Businesses

must adopt the right marketing and media strategies to reach their target markets, ensuring continuous growth in sales and profitability.

This technological shift also influences the way businesses develop their entrepreneurial capabilities and adapt to the creative economy paradigm. The creative economy requires more than just innovation, proactivity, and a willingness to take risks—key elements in the knowledge economy context. The development of the creative industry hinges on several critical factors. These include effective internal management, risk management, a strong commitment to anti-plagiarism in design, and the ability to create unique differentiating factors that set a business apart from its competitors. Furthermore, the ability to manage and process ideas has become a vital asset for industrial entrepreneurs. In an era where technology and marketing are powerful driving forces, the capacity to innovate continually and introduce new concepts to the market is essential. Businesses that can harness these aspects effectively are more likely to thrive in the competitive environment of the creative economy. Thus, technological innovation, coupled with strategic marketing, serves as a critical enabler of industrial growth and sustainability.

The advent of digital technology has revolutionized the way businesses develop, market, and distribute products, enabling the creation of new-generation products that cater to both business and consumer markets. As noted by Pradiani (2018), numerous companies are leveraging digital platforms to innovate and offer a diverse range of products that meet the evolving needs of their customers. These digital products can be broadly categorized into two main types: digital content and digital technology. Digital content refers to information that is created, stored, and distributed in a digital format. This includes a wide array of media such as video, audio, text, and graphics. These forms of content are then transformed into products that serve various business and consumer needs. For instance, digital content can be repurposed into online newspapers, magazines, educational videos, online games, photos, and other graphical representations. The versatility of digital content makes it a valuable asset for businesses aiming to engage with their audience in innovative ways, providing tailored experiences that were not possible with traditional media.

On the other hand, digital technology encompasses the tools and devices that businesses and consumers use to create, store, distribute, and interact with digital content. This includes a range of technologies, from digital video and audio equipment to more personal devices such as mobile phones, tablets, and personal digital assistants (PDAs). These technologies are critical in the digital ecosystem, as they enable the production, dissemination, and consumption of digital content across various platforms. For example, mobile phones have become indispensable tools not only for communication but also for consuming a wide variety of digital content such as streaming video, playing online games, and accessing digital news. The synergy between digital content and digital technology has led to a dynamic marketplace where businesses can rapidly innovate and offer products that are highly responsive to consumer demands. This integration allows companies to reach broader audiences and deliver personalized experiences, which are increasingly important in today's digital economy. Moreover, the ability to continually update and enhance digital

products ensures that businesses can maintain a competitive edge by adapting to new technological advancements and consumer preferences.

Pasuruan Regency, encompassing an area of 1,474.015 km², is strategically situated between 112°35'30" to 113°06'30" East Longitude and 7°32'30" to 7°57'30" South Latitude. The region is bordered to the north by Pasuruan City, the Madura Strait, and Sidoarjo Regency; to the south by Malang Regency; to the west by Mojokerto Regency and Batu City; and to the east by Probolinggo Regency (Pasuruan Regency Government, 2022).

The regency is home to a wide variety of small or household industries, reflecting the diverse economic activities in the area. These industries include processed food, beverages, clothing (convection), and furniture, particularly wood crafts. For instance, Gempol District is well-known for its centers producing traditional snacks such as bakpia and klepon, as well as ready-to-wear clothing. Meanwhile, Bangil District is recognized for its embroidery work, which is also prominent in other areas such as Beji and Rembang, where products like mukena and Muslim clothing are produced.

Woodcraft industries are particularly notable in villages such as Sentul in Purwodadi District, Tambaksari in Kraton District, Wonorejo in Wonorejo District, and Sungikulon and Sungiwetan in Pohjentrek District. Additional centers are found in Winongan District and Rejoso District. The range of products from these areas includes children's toys, car steering wheels, tissue boxes, gear shift handles, dashboards, chess sets, and various types of furniture. Many of these small industry products not only cater to local demand but also reach markets outside the region and even abroad, indicating a significant contribution to export activities.

The Gempol UMKM Community is a collective of entrepreneurs engaged in various types of businesses, each offering different products. According to data from the Pasuruan Regency website, the Gempol area predominantly consists of household businesses specializing in food and beverage processing. The products from this area include a variety of wet foods, such as brownies and crispy chicken, as well as dry foods like tempeh chips, fried peanuts, herbal medicine, and more. This diversity highlights the entrepreneurial spirit and the economic potential of the Gempol UMKM Community in contributing to the broader regional economy.

This community service activity was carried out in accordance with the steps that have been determined. In the initial stage, communication was carried out with Mrs. Sudiati as the owner of the Dua Putri UMKM processed catfish in Ngerong, Gempol, Pasuruan, East Java via WhatsApp which had been provided by the Pasuruan Regional Cooperative Service. From the resource person, the information we obtained was that the majority of UMKM product sales in the Gempol area, Pasuruan were still experiencing difficulties in marketing their products. The products they sell have gone through a complete legality process, starting from P-IRT, SKP, to halal certification. In fact, they have marketed their products through online shops such as Shopee, GoFood, and Grab Food. However, online sales are still not optimal due to the absence of an admin on standby to answer orders via WhatsApp

or other relevant social media. Therefore, it is necessary to improve WhatsApp media to become WhatsApp Business as an online sales platform.

The steps for setting up WhatsApp Business are as follows:

1. Preparation Before Setup: Before you begin setting up your business profile, ensure you understand how to start using WhatsApp Business. Here are some things you need to prepare:
 - a. New Contacts: Consider using a new contact number specifically for WhatsApp Business.
 - b. Old Contacts: If you prefer to continue using your existing contact number, be aware that this number will migrate to WhatsApp Business, meaning it will no longer be available for personal WhatsApp use.
2. Download the Application: Go to the Play Store and search for the WhatsApp Business application. Once found, tap the Install button.
3. Open the Application: After the installation is complete, open the WhatsApp Business application.

Figure 1. WhatsApp Business download display

4. Agree to Terms and Conditions: Tap the 'Agree & Continue' or 'Agree and Continue' option to proceed.
5. Enter Your Phone Number: In the next step, you will need to enter the phone number that you want to use for your WhatsApp Business account.
6. Verify Your Number: WhatsApp will send a verification code to your phone via SMS. Enter the verification code in the application and click Continue.

Figure 2. Verification code display on the WhatsApp Business page

7. Backup Restoration Option: WhatsApp may ask if you want to restore a backup. If this account is new or if you don't have a backup to restore, you can choose the 'Later' option.
8. Finalization: Once these steps are completed, your WhatsApp Business account setup is done. You can now proceed to customize your business profile and start using the app for business communications.

Figure 3. Implementation of Creating Whatsapp Business

After successfully installing WhatsApp Business on the cellphones of each UMKM group member in the Gempol area, the next crucial step was to set up their business profiles and fill in the necessary information. This process is a significant milestone as it directly benefits each UMKM participant by enhancing their ability to interact with customers in a more professional and efficient manner. WhatsApp Business is particularly useful because it offers features that allow business owners to automate responses, sort messages, and reply quickly. These capabilities are essential for improving communication, ensuring prompt customer service, and ultimately

building stronger relationships with customers. The next phase of the initiative involves introducing participants to website creation as a key component of branding and digital marketing. The website serves as a central platform where businesses can showcase their products, share their brand story, and reach a wider audience. The training begins with an introduction to free website options, which are accessible and easy to use for small business owners. This foundational knowledge is essential for participants who may be new to digital tools and need a straightforward entry point.

Following the introduction, the training delves into optimizing web design. Participants learn how to create a visually appealing and user-friendly website that effectively communicates their brand message. This includes guidance on layout, color schemes, typography, and content placement, all of which contribute to a professional online presence. By the end of this phase, participants not only understand the importance of having a website but also gain practical skills to design and maintain a website that supports their business goals. Overall, the combination of WhatsApp Business setup and website creation provides UMKM participants in Gempol with powerful tools to enhance their digital presence, streamline customer interactions, and expand their market reach. These steps are integral to the broader goal of empowering local businesses to thrive in the digital economy.

Figure 4. Web design optimization

The initiative to create free websites for SME (Small and Medium Enterprises) participants is a valuable practice that allows them to enhance their online presence while learning essential digital skills. Although participants work on creating their websites independently from home, continuous support is provided through coordination via a WhatsApp group. This approach ensures that participants can receive guidance and troubleshooting assistance as they progress, fostering a sense of community and collaborative learning.

The primary benefit of creating a website for SME actors is that it serves as a powerful promotional tool. A well-designed website can significantly increase the

visibility and credibility of a business, engaging viewers more effectively than traditional methods. While free websites may offer basic functionality and limited features, they still provide a valuable starting point for businesses that are new to digital marketing. However, it's important to recognize that transitioning to a professional website can greatly enhance a business's reputation and trustworthiness, leading to better customer engagement and potentially higher sales.

An example of this effort is the website created for Mrs. Sudarti's business, "Davita," which specializes in processed catfish products. By establishing an online presence through a dedicated website, her business can reach a broader audience, showcase its products more effectively, and compete more favorably in the market. This dedication to helping SME actors like Mrs. Sudarti is not just about creating a website; it also involves ongoing support to ensure the website is fully developed and maintained. Periodic accompaniment is planned to ensure that the website remains functional, up-to-date, and continues to meet the evolving needs of the business.

Figure 5. Davita Patin Processing Website

After the presentation by the community service group from the Faculty of Economics, UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, the session transitioned into a lively and engaging question-and-answer segment. The enthusiasm from the participants was evident, reflecting their eagerness to apply the knowledge shared during the presentation to their respective businesses. Given the diversity in the participants' businesses and age groups, the challenges they face vary significantly, leading to a wide range of questions and concerns. One of the most pressing issues that arose during this session was the difficulty some participants experienced with installing the WhatsApp Business application on their smartphones. For some, their devices were unable to support the application, which is a significant hurdle in adopting this digital tool. The solution provided by the community service group was to first ensure

that all applications on the smartphone are up to date. Updating the smartphone's operating system and existing applications can often resolve compatibility issues, allowing for the successful installation of new apps like WhatsApp Business.

However, a more substantial problem occurs if a participant's smartphone is fundamentally incompatible with the WhatsApp Business application. This issue is particularly challenging because it may require the participants to upgrade their devices, which can be a significant financial burden, especially for small business owners. The group likely discussed alternative solutions, such as using WhatsApp Web through a browser or utilizing other communication tools that the participants' devices might support. This question-and-answer session highlighted the practical challenges faced by UMKM participants in adopting digital tools and underscored the importance of providing tailored solutions that consider the varying technological capabilities of different users. The session's success in addressing these concerns helps to ensure that all participants, regardless of their initial technological limitations, can benefit from the digitalization efforts and improve their business operations.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Based on the description and discussion above, it can be concluded that this activity program is a significant component of the community service initiatives undertaken by the Lecturers and the Faculty of Economics at UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang. The UMKM mentoring program aims to make a tangible impact on the branding and sales of products within the local community, particularly among small and medium enterprises. By equipping these businesses with the knowledge and tools necessary to enhance their digital presence, the program seeks to contribute to the broader goal of economic welfare in small communities.

The expected outcomes of this program extend beyond just economic benefits; they also encompass social advantages, fostering community harmony, and promoting environmental sustainability. Through this holistic approach, the program not only supports the economic empowerment of UMKM actors but also contributes to the overall well-being and cohesion of the community. This initiative serves as a model for how academic institutions can play a crucial role in uplifting local economies while addressing the multifaceted needs of society.

Suggestions

To maximize the impact of this community service initiative, it is recommended that such activities be conducted regularly and periodically. By doing so, the program can continuously support and address the evolving needs of the community. These activities should be implemented not only in the current location but also extended to other areas with different challenges and community needs. This approach will allow for a more comprehensive and adaptable program that can provide tailored solutions to diverse situations, thereby ensuring that the benefits of community service reach a broader audience and contribute to the sustainable development of various communities.

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